

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
AUTOMATIC ROOM LIGHT CONTROLLER MANAGEMENT
SYSTEM
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EMBEDDED

SYSTEMS

“EMBEDDED SYSTEM”

❖ WHAT ARE EMBEDDED SYSTEMS?

Embedded systems are the developing system at this time. The combination of hardware and software components that are embedded into a system to make it interact intelligently with its (physical) environment to meet a specific need with performance in given time. In one line we can say

Embedded System = Computers Inside a Product

Examples:-

**Digital
Television**

**Lithography
Systems**

**Medical
Systems**

**Mobile
Phones**

**Automotive
Systems**

**Digital
Printers**

**Military
Systems**

**Control
Systems**

Important fact:-

**PC microprocessors are responsible for less than
1% of all processors sold.**

**Embedded processors outsell PC processors by
more than 99%.**

Characteristics of embedded system

- ⇒ Perform a single set of functions.
- ⇒ Works in time constrained environment.
- ⇒ Complete automation.
- ⇒ Provide high performance and reliability.
- ⇒ Low cost (mostly) because they are mass produced in billions.
- ⇒ Qualitative & reliable.
- ⇒ Small Size, Low Weight.
- ⇒ Low Power consumption.
- ⇒ Some embedded systems have mechanical moving parts like disk drives as they are less reliable as compare to solid state parts such as flash memory.

-: APPLICATION:-

⇒ Telecom:-

Mobile phones systems (handsets & base stations),
Modems, Routers, etc.

⇒ Automotive applications:-

Breaking systems, Traction control, Airbag release
system, Engine management systems, Steer-by-
wire systems, Cruise control applications.

⇒ Domestic applications:-

Dishwashers, TV, Washing machines, Microwave
ovens, Video recorders, Security systems, Garage
door controllers, Calculators, Digital watches,
Digital cameras, Remote control, etc.

⇒ Robotics:-

Fire fighting robots, Automatic floor cleaners,
robotic arms, etc.

⇒ Aerospace applications:-

Flight control systems, Autopilots, Passenger in-
flight entertainment systems.

⇒ Medical equipments:-

An aesthesia monitoring systems, ECG monitors,

Pacemakers, Drug delivery systems, MRI scanners.

⇒ **Defense systems:-**

RADAR systems, Fighter aircrafts, Radio systems, missile guidance systems, etc.

⇒ **Office automation:-**

Laser printers, Fax machines, Papers, Gas pumps, Credit/debit card readers, thermostats, etc.

:- Various Embedded Computing Areas:-

⇒ **Small embedded controllers:-**

- 8-bit CPUs dominate, simple or no operating system. E.g. thermostats.

⇒ **Control systems:-**

- Often use DSP (Digital Signal Processing) chip for control computations. E.g. auto-motive engine control.

⇒ **Distributed embedded control:-**

- Mixture of large and small nodes on a

real-time embedded network. E.g. cars,
elevators

⇒ **System on chip:-**

- ASIC design tailored to application area.
E.g. consumer electronics, set-top boxes.

⇒ **Network equipment:-**

- Emphasis on data movement/packet flow.
e.g., network switches, telephone switches.

⇒ **Critical systems:-**

- Safety & mission critical computing. E.g.
pacemakers, automatic trains

⇒ **Signal processing:-**

- Often use DSP chips for vision, audio, or
other signal processing. E.g. face recognition

⇒ **Robotics:-**

- Uses various types of embedded computing
(especially vision and control). E.g.
autonomous vehicles

⇒ **Computer peripherals**

- Disk drives, keyboards, laser printers, etc.

⇒ **Wireless systems**

- Wireless network-connected “sensor-networks” and “motes” to gather and report information

⇒ **Embedded PCs**

- Palmtop and small form factor PCs embedded into equipment

⇒ **Command and control**

- Often huge military systems and “systems of systems”. E.g. a fleet of warships with interconnected computer

MICROCONTROLLER

8051

8051-MICROCONTROLLER

- ⇒ Developed by *Intel corporation* in year 1981
- ⇒ It was called as a “system on a chip”.
- ⇒ Intel refers to it as MSC-51 now.

DISCRIPTION:-

The AT89S51 is a low-power, high-performance CMOS 8-bit microcontroller with 4K bytes of In-System Programmable Flash memory. The device is manufactured using Atmel’s high-density non-volatile memory technology and is compatible with the industry-standard 80C51 instruction set and pin-out. The on-chip Flash allows the program memory to be reprogrammed in-system or by a conventional non-volatile memory programmer. By combining a versatile 8-bit CPU with In-System Programmable Flash on a monolithic chip, the Atmel AT89S51 is a powerful microcontroller which provides a highly-flexible and cost-effective solution to many embedded control applications. The AT89S51

provides the following standard features: 4K bytes of Flash, 128 bytes of RAM, 32 I/O lines, Watchdog timer, two data pointers, two 16-bit timer/counters, a five-vector two-level interrupt architecture, a full duplex serial port, on-chip oscillator, and clock circuitry. In addition, the AT89S51 is designed with static logic for operation down to zero frequency and supports two software selectable power saving modes. The Idle Mode stops the CPU while allowing the RAM, timer/counters, serial port, and interrupt system to continue functioning. The Power-down mode saves the RAM contents but freezes the oscillator, disabling all other chip functions until the next external interrupt or hardware reset.

STANDERD FEATURES OF THE 8051

- ⇒ 8-BIT data path and ALU.
- ⇒ On chip flash memory.
- ⇒ 5K X 8—ROM- Program memory.
- ⇒ 128 X 8—RAM- Data memory.
- ⇒ Multiple 16-BIT timer/counter.

- ⇒ Full duplex UART (serial port).
- ⇒ On chip clock oscillator.
- ⇒ 32 I/O pins.
- ⇒ Six interrupt sources.

FAMILY MEMBERS OF μ C -8051

Features	8051	8031	8052	8032
ROM	4k	0k	8k	0k
RAM	128	128	256	256
Timers	2	2	3	3
I/O pins	32	32	32	32
Serial port	1	1	1	1
Interrupt sources	6	6	7	7

Intel allows other manufacturers to and markets any version of 8051 depending upon the speed and on-chip ROM. There are more than 50 companies like ST, TI, SIEMENS, WINBONDS etc. marketing micro-controller base on Intel-8051.

-: PIN DESCRIPTION:-

⇒ **Port 0 — pins (32 - 39) :-**

- Input/output pins.
- Required external pull-up register of 10 k ohm.
- Used as I/O port and higher address byte.

⇒ **Prot 1 — pins (1 - 8) :-**

- i/o pins
- Contains internal pull-ups.

⇒ **Prot 2 — pins (21 - 28) :-**

- i/o pins
- Contains internal pull-ups..
- Used as I/O port and higher address byte

⇒ **Prot 3 — pins (10 - 17) :-**

- i/o pins
- Contains internal pull-ups.
- Alternate function to provide signal such as interrupts.

⇒ **PSEN – (pin 29) :- Program store enable**

- Active low input.
- Used while accessing external memory
- Connected to OE pin of external ROM.

⇒ **ALE -- (pin 30) :- Address latch enable**

- Active high.
- Used for de-multiplexing the address & data by connecting G pin of the 74LS373.

⇒ **EA – (pin 31) :-**

- Active low input.
- To excess external ROM it must be connected to GND.

⇒ **XTAL1 & XTAL2 – (pins 18 & 19):-**

- Provide electric field to quartz oscillator for oscillations.

⇒ **RESET – (pin 9) :-**

- Active high input.
- Terminates all activities of microcontroller.
- Set PC to 0000h.
- Requires minimum 2 machine cycles.

⇒ *VCC* – (*pin 40*)

⇒ *GND* –(*pin 20*)

CRYSTAL CONNECTIONS

The capacitor C1 & C2 are of 33 pF each. It provides clocks to 8051 for its operations.

As described above XTAL1 and XTAL2 are connected to pin no 18 and 19 of controller and pin 20 is grounded.

-:MEMORY ORGANIZATION:-

MCS-51 devices have a separate address space for **Program** and **Data Memory**. Up to 64K bytes each of external Program and Data Memory can be addressed.

Program Memory :-

If the EA pin is connected to GND, all program fetches are directed to external memory. On the AT89S51, if EA is connected to VCC, program

fetches to addresses 0000H through FFFH are directed to internal memory and fetches to addresses 1000H through FFFFH are directed to external memory.

Data Memory :-

The AT89S51 implements 128 bytes of on-chip RAM. The 128 bytes are accessible via direct and indirect addressing modes. Stack operations are examples of indirect addressing, so the 128 bytes of data RAM are available as stack space.

Internal data memory

- **Lower 128 bytes** : **00H – 7FH**
- **Four register bank** : **00H – 1FH**
- **Bit addressable area** : **20H – 2Fh**
- **General purpose area** : **30H – 7Fh**
- **SFR address space** : **80H – FFH**

INSTRUCTION SET OF uC-8051

- **full instruction set includes :**
 - i. Airthemetic Instructions*
 - ii. Logical Instructions*
 - iii. Branching Instructions*
 - iv. Data movement Instructions.*

▪ **AIRTHEMATIC INSTRUCTIONS :**

<i>MNEMONICS</i>	<i>OPERANDS</i>	<i>BYTES/CYCLES</i>
<i>ADD</i>	<i>A, Rn</i>	<i>1/1</i>
<i>SUBB</i>	<i>A, direct</i>	<i>2/1</i>
<i>ADDC</i>	<i>A, @Ri</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>A, #data</i>	<i>2/1</i>
<i>INC</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>1/1</i>
<i>DEC</i>	<i>Rn</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>direct</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>@Ri</i>	<i>1/1</i>
<i>MUL</i>	<i>DPTR</i>	<i>1/2</i>
<i>INC</i>	<i>AB</i>	<i>1/4</i>
<i>DIV</i>	<i>AB</i>	<i>1/4</i>
<i>DA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>1/1</i>

LOGICAL INSTRUCTIONS

MNEMONICS	OPERANDS	BYTES/CYCLES
ANL	<i>A, Rn</i>	<i>1/1</i>
OR	<i>A, direct</i>	<i>2/1</i>
XRL	<i>A, @Ri</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>A, #data</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>Direct, A</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>Direct,#data</i>	<i>3/2</i>
	<i>C, bit</i>	<i>2/2</i>
	<i>C, /bit</i>	<i>2/2</i>
CLR	<i>A</i>	<i>1/1</i>
CPL	<i>C</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>Bit</i>	<i>2/1</i>
RL, RLC	<i>A</i>	<i>1/1</i>
RR,RRC	<i>(FOR ALL)</i>	<i>1/1</i>
SWAP		<i>1/1</i>
		<i>1/1</i>
SET	<i>C</i>	<i>1/1</i>
CLR	<i>C</i>	<i>1/1</i>
CLP	<i>bit</i>	<i>2/1</i>

DATA TRANSFER INSTRUCTIONS

<i>MNEMONICS</i>	<i>OPERANDS</i>	<i>BYTES/CYCLES</i>
<i>MOV</i>	<i>A, Rn</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>A, direct</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>A, @Ri</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>A, #data</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>Rn A,</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>Rn, direct</i>	<i>2/2</i>
	<i>Rn, #data</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>direct, A</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>direct, Rn</i>	<i>2/2</i>
	<i>direct, direct</i>	<i>3/2</i>
	<i>direct, @Ri</i>	<i>2/2</i>
	<i>direct, #data</i>	<i>3/2</i>
<i>MOV</i>	<i>@Ri, A</i>	<i>1/1</i>
	<i>@Ri, direct</i>	<i>2/2</i>
	<i>@Ri, #data</i>	<i>2/1</i>
	<i>DPTR, #data16</i>	<i>3/2</i>
	<i>C, bit</i>	<i>2/1</i>

MOV	bit, C	2/2
MOVB	A, @DPTR	1/2
	@DPTR, A	1/2
	A, @Ri	1/2
	@Ri, A	1/2
MOVC	A, @A+DPTR	1/2
	A, @A+PC	1/2
PUSH	direct	2/2
POP	direct	2/2
XCH	A, Rn	1/1
	A, direct	2/1
	A, @Ri	1/1
XCHD	A, @Ri	1/1

BRANCHING INSTRUCTIONC

<i>MNEMONICS</i>	<i>OPERANDS</i>	<i>BYTES/CYCLES</i>
<i>JC,JNC</i>	<i>rel</i>	<i>2/2</i>
<i>JB,JNB,JBC</i>	<i>bit, rel</i>	<i>3/2</i>
<i>JN,JNZ</i>	<i>rel</i>	<i>2/2</i>
<i>LJMP,AJMP</i>	<i>addr16/11</i>	<i>3,2/2</i>
<i>SJMP</i>	<i>rel</i>	<i>2/2</i>
<i>JMP</i>	<i>@A+DPTR</i>	<i>1/2</i>
<i>LCALL,ACALL</i>	<i>addr16/11</i>	<i>3,2/2</i>
<i>RET, RETI</i>	<i>--</i>	<i>1/2</i>
<i>CJNE</i>	<i>A,direct,rel</i>	<i>3/2</i>
	<i>A,#data,rel</i>	<i>3/2</i>
	<i>Rn,#data,rel</i>	<i>3/2</i>
	<i>@Ri,#data,rel</i>	<i>3/2</i>
<i>DJNE</i>	<i>Rn,reL</i>	<i>2/2</i>
	<i>direct,rel</i>	<i>3/2</i>
<i>NOP</i>	<i>--</i>	<i>1/1</i>

ABOUT **PROJECT**

Introduction to project

This project is developed for people who are interested in automation of homes, offices, halls, etc. This technology is currently under a great progress. This project is just an image of device automation using embedded technologies.

This project use embedded technology in which we use 8051 micro-controller with different electronics components. This project will control lights of a room. It will switch in the lights automatically as a person enters into the room and switch them as all people left the room.

In further modification of this project we can control the more devices like fan, ac and many more by slight changes like controlling of the temperature of a room by this project by using temperature controlled fan/ac.

Tools used in project

This project programming is developed in assembly language. The other main tools which we have used in this project are listed below:-

1. 8051 Burner:-

The 8051 burner is a Microcontroller IC programmer for AT89S51/52 ICs.

2. 8051 IDE:-

The 8051 IDE combines a text editor, assembler, and software simulator into a single program. All components that are needed to develop 8051 programs are available and controllable from this single IDE running on Windows 2000 and XP.

3. Keil Compiler:-

Keil PK51 is a complete software development environment for classic and extended 8051 micro-controllers.

Block diagram:-

-:TECHNOLOGY PLATEFORM:-

- It uses 8-bit 8051 microcontroller.
- Programming is accomplished by 8051IDE which is an assembly language interface.
- We used optocouplers as sensors.
- Seven segments are used as display device.

Hardware description

We have used many different electronics components into this project like **Microcontroller (AT89S52), seven-segments, LED's, sensors, relays, optocouplers, different resistances**. There is the description of some of the major components:-

1. Micro-controller:-

In this project AT89S52 is used.

The AT89S52 is a CMOS 8-bit microcontroller with 8K bytes of in-system programmable Flash memory & is compatible with the industry-standard 80C51 instruction set and pin out. The on-chip Flash allows the program memory to be reprogrammed in-system or by a conventional non-volatile memory programmer.

2. Optocouplers:-

In this project optocoupler **MOC7811** is used. It is used to sense the entering or leaving the room by any person. It consists of an infrared light emitting diode coupled to an N-P-N silicon phototransistor packaged into injection molded housing. The housing is designed for wide gap, non contact sensing.

DIAGRAM

H-SHAPED OPTOCOUPLER

We have used *two optocouplers* one for sensing entering and other for sensing exiting.

3. Segment display:-

It is the most common type of display used in embedded system. It has seven leds in it one for each segment. They are commonly used in Calculators, micro-waves, stereos, VCR's, TV and many more household applications. They can be viewed from 8 meters. We use *2 seven* segments as display device.

These seven segments are of two types:-

1. Common anode
2. Common cathode

Each seven-segment display is an individual light emitting diode. A diode is made up of a p-n junction with has a basic property to allow the current to flow only in one direction.

4. RELAYS:-

A relay is an electrically operated switch. It is also called electromechanical switch made up of electro-magnets and allows one circuit to switch to a second circuit which can be completely separated from first. We have used *one relay* switch operating at *12v*.

5. CRYSTAL OSCILLATOR:-

A simplified schematic of the oscillator circuit used in this project is shown in the previous section. Its pins are connected to 18 & 19 pins of uC. The value of capacitors is *33pF*.

6. RESISTORS & CAPICITORS:-

In this project

multiple valued resistors and capacitors are used.

Here is the details of resistors :-

6 resistor of 2.2 k ohm (in different ckts.)

10 resistor of 1 k ohm (for LED connections)

2 resistors of 330 ohm (for optocouplers)

1 capacitor of 10pf (across pin 9)

Some pictures of resistors and capacitors:-

7. BUZZER:-

Buzzers are made up of piezo electric crystals. It produces oscillations when electric field is applied to it upto frequency range of 20Hz to 20 kHz So it can be heard easily. Thus sound/alarm is produced . In this project one buzzer is used for alarming purpose. A general buzzer is shown below :

-: WORKING IDEA OF PROJECT:-

In this project we have used two optocouplers as sensors. Whenever anybody enters in the room (can be modelled by swiping a card b/w gate is opto.) the rays are cut by him and it is detected as signal 0 by the microcontroller and it will set the relay by sending 1 or 0 accordingly to the i/p of relay and lights will be switched on and counter is incremented by 1 showing the single person entrance in the room & display this to display device. Now for next entry it will just increment the counter by one. This will continue until the no. of person entering in the room is not equal to a pre-decided limit. As the limit crosses that value and as anybody try to enter the buzzer will start alarming indicating the entry of extra person. Now for the exiting case, as a person exit from the room it will be sensed by microcontroller and it will decrement the counter by one. It will continue to decrement the counter with every exit until the room is not empty which is sensed when the value of counter will become zero and microcontroller commands relay to switch off the light. In this way the lights of a room are controlled with counting the entries by this project.

-: FEATURES:-

1) RELIABLE:-

With more use of more practical sensors and microcontroller this project is quit reliable.

2) FASTER RESPONSE:-

In this project we use microcontroller with the response time in terms of microseconds. So this projects is has faster response.

3) AUTOMATIC:-

Once programmed the microcontroller takes up the responsibilities of operating it.

4) CHEAPER:-

With large production coming up the production cost of electric goods has decreased dramatically.

5) APPLICABLE TO SMALL AS WELL AS LARGER LEVELS:-

It can be used as a counter for people by using “LASER” and “LDR”, coupling as sensors or at a lover level by using an optocoupler.

6) SMALL POWER REQUIREMENT:-

It consumes less power approximate 12v and also eliminates the danger of electric shock.

7) HUMAN INRTFACING:-

Human interfacing is possible by using LCD and LED (seven segments).

:-USES:-

- IN HOTELS.
- IN COMMERCIAL COMPLEXCES.
- HOUSES

:- ADVANTAGES:-

- Cost effective
- Reliable
- Very useful for blind and deaf people
- Operated with same electricity source

- Can be used in hotels, banquet hall where exact no. of people can be counted and hence no wastage of food.

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